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JUSTICE-BASED SOCIAL WORK INTERVENTION: A CASE STUDY

ADALET TEMELLİ SOSYAL HİZMET MÜDAHALESİ: BİR VAKA ÇALIŞMASI

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Özet

Güçlendirme, 1980'li yıllardan itibaren sosyal hizmet mesleğinde kullanılan yaklaşımların başında gelmekle birlikte, her ne kadar gücü paylaştığı için eleştirilse de bu yaklaşımlardan biridir. Bu yaklaşımın olumlu yanı, diğer yaklaşımlarla eklektik olarak kullanılabilmesidir. Yaklaşımın temeli, insanların kendilerini geliştirme potansiyeline sahip oldukları inancıdır. Bu düşünce ile insana değer vermeyen sorunları hastalığın boyutuna indirgeyen tıbbi yaklaşıma bir alternatiftir. Bu nedenle, güçlendirme hem bir süreç hem de bir sonuçtur. Bu çalışmada güçlendirmenin tarihsel temelleri, güçlendirme ile ilgili kavramlar, güçlendirmenin temel varsayımları ve sınırlılıklarına yer verilmiştir. Türkiye'de 2000'li yıllardan bu yana güçlendirme ile ilgili bilimsel yayınlarda artış olmasına rağmen, yaklaşımları vaka örnekleriyle analiz eden az sayıda çalışma bulunmaktadır. Bu çalışma ile alanda çalışan sosyal hizmet uzmanlarının zayıf yönlerini ve potansiyellerini görmeleri sağlanarak kuramın vaka örnekleri ile irdelenmeye çalışılmıştır. Böylece ülkede artan eşitsizlik, adaletsizlik ve insan hakları gibi toplumsal sorunların çözümüne alternatif bir bakış açısı sunulmaya çalışılacaktır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Güçlendirme, sosyal hizmet, hümanizm, adalet, zayıflık

Abstract

Empowerment is one of the primary approaches used in the social work profession starting from the 1980s, although it has been criticized for sharing power. The positive side of this approach is that it can be used eclectically with other approaches. The basis of the approach is the belief that people have the potential to improve themselves. With this idea, it is an alternative to the medical approach that reduces problems that do not value people to the size of the disease. Thus, empowerment is both a process and a result. In this study, the historical foundations of empowerment, concepts related to empowerment, basic assumptions and limitations of empowerment are included. Although there has been an increase in scientific publications on empowerment in Turkey since the 2000s, there are few studies analyzing the approaches with case examples. With this study, it is tried to examine the theory with case examples by enabling social workers working in the field to see their weaknesses and potentials. Thus, it will be tried to provide an alternative perspective to the solution of social problems such as increasing inequality, injustice and human rights in the country.

Keywords: Empowerment, social work, humanism, justice, weakness

Introduction

The quality of the relationship between the counselor and the client is considered to be the turning point in effective intervention. When clinical research is considered, beyond the nature of social work intervention, social work practices are at the focus of this interaction. Despite the inequality in the use of power between the social worker and the client, mutual volunteerism, trust and interaction are determinant in the empowerment approach. In this approach, there is no one-way communication between the counselor and the client depending on the authority (Hasenfeld, 1987:470). The approaches that examined the client from a clinical perspective, which were among the first examples of social work practices, saw the individual as the source of problems. Therefore, clinical approaches did not impose responsibility on social workers. The view of clinical approaches that saw people as worthless was abandoned over time and the empowerment approach emerged.

Empowerment-based approaches aim to enable the individual to use his/her potential against pressures and to address the lack of power or control. With this approach, it enables the applicant to access opportunities and resources that may occur in and around the applicant by cooperating with the social worker and the applicant against pressure or power centers. This intervention can be applied with individuals, groups and society (Teater, 2015). Another purpose of empowerment is to enable the individual to stand on his/her own feet and accept responsibility for his/her life experiences. In the client's journey with the counselor, the obstacles that challenge him/her can be seen as an opportunity and it is revealed that the source of power can actually be in every person (Erbay, 2019:42-43). In a sense, the client discovers himself/herself and develops insight.

The empowerment approach is a result as well as a process. The approach starts with the client's dissatisfaction with his/her situation and the desire for change. It is the client who will determine the result and realize his/her development in the process.

In this study, the historical course of the empowerment approach is mentioned, information about power and how it is found in human beings is given, the aspects of the empowerment approach that differ from other theories are discussed, and in the last part, the important concepts of the empowerment approach are mentioned through the case example. Considering that there are few studies supported by case presentations in the social work literature, it is thought that the relevant study will make an important contribution to social work studies in Turkey.

HISTORICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE RETROFITTING APPROACH

The strengths perspective in social work has its philosophical roots in Aristotle's teleological theory of human development or eudaimonia. Eudaimonism argues that people should strive to reach their innate potential by using their talents, most importantly their intellect and intelligence. It grounds ethics in human nature and links human development to the pursuit of virtues. Therefore, values exist because of the needs and requirements of human beings. Eudaimonia is based on the idea that one must make one's own choices in order to achieve virtues and that they exist through their choices (Gray, 2011:5). Empowerment, which evolved from philosophical movements, was later used frequently in areas such as personal development, NLP, coaching, as well as in education, health services, and advocacy.

The empowerment approach, which emerged as an alternative to the clinical approach, started to become widespread in Britain at the end of the 1980s. The time when this approach was most accepted was the mid-1990s. In Britain, empowerment has been in existence since the eighteenth century as mutual aid in charitable organizations (Leadbetter, 2002). In the history of social work in America, the settlement movement, Jane Addams' work, the women's club, social reform movements for African Americans in the 19th century, empowerment approaches for minority groups, Reynolds' radical psychoanalytic approach (Lee and Hudson, 2011:161).

In America, where empowerment laid the foundation, women did not have the right to vote and be elected, they did not have the right to divorce unless there was an event that would harm the society, they could not freely enroll in the university they wanted, and women could not engage in empowerment approaches as social workers. Jane Addams and her friends pioneered in ensuring gender equality, ensuring social justice, and providing a multicultural social structure (Lee and Hudson, 2011: 161-162). Therefore, a parallel relationship has emerged between the struggles for democracy and human rights in America and empowerment theories. The philosophical and economic basis of the empowerment approach is the mutual and fair distribution of resources without class differences.

The influence of African American women's associations in the fight against racism in America is important. African American church congregations and aid groups established by African Americans have played a driving role in the adoption of the role of black women by

the masses. African American women's associations have done serious work on civil rights in cooperation with white women. Group action and taking social responsibility for democratic values, which are used in group work in social work, were shaped by the anti-racist political environment in America (Shapiro, 1991).

In the history of American social work, the Great Depression also had important consequences. This process did not bring advantages for workers except partial social security practices. Social workers could not develop social work practices against the difficulties of the macro economy that developed during this period. Berta Reynolds, as an exception, developed an approach based on advocacy and emphasizing social justice instead of psychoanalytic intervention approach in this period. In this political environment, the client is a simple person, not a person seeking professional help. The empowered individual should interact with opportunities and resources that increase potential and the individual should not lose this connection (Reynolds, 1951).

In the empowerment theory of social work, the theories of social sciences such as political science, psychology, sociology and economics are used (Lee and Hudson, 2011). According to some thinkers, emancipation better reflects the goals and intervention processes of the empowerment approach.

The empowerment approach in social work has had two main pillars: political, political, economic movements and medical approaches to human development. The concept of power has been shaped as a result of these social movements and medical approaches (Lee and Hudson, 2011:162-163).

STRENGTH AND EMPOWERMENT

According to the empowerment approach, three types of power can be mentioned: personal power, interpersonal power and political power. These powers are interrelated. Personal power is the power within the limits that determine the potential of the individual. Interpersonal power includes his/her prestige and the power to influence others. Political power provides solidarity with vulnerable people against pressure groups and creates political consciousness. A decrease in one of the powers negatively affects other types of power.

This idea, which emerged in the 1960s, is frequently used in school social work and psychology (Duyan, 2016). In this approach, which has been adopted since the 1960s, it is ensured that the person realizes his/her weaknesses and strengths and establishes life

balance.

There are criticisms among social work theorists that the client is not sufficiently empowered in this approach. Theorists such as Steiner think that the person cannot be empowered in this approach and thinks that he/she is saved. Thus, the blockages that consume the power of the person are renewed and cause the person to remain powerless (Adams, 2017: 6). These radicalist criticisms of the empowerment approach have led to a better understanding of the approach. Over time, it has been understood that without the empowerment approach, a holistic view of social problems cannot be realized with other theories of social work.

According to Thomas and Piercon (1995:134-5), empowerment is the ability of groups to help themselves, to initiate an intervention process of their own volition and to consult social services in cooperation or independently. According to Adams (2017), empowerment is the ability of individuals, groups and society to take control of their life conditions and to help themselves and others.

CONCEPTS OF RETROFITTING

Empowerment has various control mechanisms in individuals, groups and communities. These are self-determinism, self-esteem, vital competence, self-efficacy and internal control mechanisms (Greene et al., 2005). Situations far from empowerment are determined by the weakness of these concepts. Low self-esteem causes the person to feel worthless, and the feeling of learned helplessness makes people believe that they have no influence in their lives. Therefore, these are psychological barriers that weaken the person's application to the counselor with the desire for change.

Self-efficacy is the individual's perception of being adequate in the new job and the responsibility he/she takes. It is important in empowering the person like other positive psychological factors.

When a person is under external influence, he/she may think that the flow of life is not in himself/herself, but in the leaders, political power, maybe in his/her family, around his/her mother or father. The individual cannot make his/her decisions freely in order not to upset others and to get along with them in harmony. The control of his/her life is always in someone else's sphere of influence unless he/she realizes it himself/herself. In this type of people, the need to go to a counselor increases in moments of crisis that concern the whole family and individuals, such as a sudden resignation from a job, loss of a family member, increase in poverty, etc. Internal psychological states are now less affected by external influences. Thus,

the individual tries to increase his power by learning from his experiences (Greene et al., 2005). According to Lee and Hudson (2011), by developing a healthy identity and a positive self, people develop awareness of the pressures imposed on themselves and the people around them. Therefore, people who develop awareness can use their personal and environmental resources more efficiently.

Self-determinism is a concept that dates back to the French Revolution. In short, it is the right to determine one's life and the freedom to choose. It entered the social work literature with the freedom of choice and determination in the democratization process of nations as a result of political and economic developments. The client is the person who actively initiates the intervention process and is the person who has the freedom to choose in the intervention process. He is the person who should take the flow of his life into his own hands with his own will. In this context, self-help is an antidote of the client against the power used professionally by the counselor. Legislators are expected to make regulations on these issues (Thomas and Pierson, 1995:474-475). When considered around these concepts, taking action, making choices, maintaining well-being are important goals of the approach.

The ability of the individual to realize his/her potential and use his/her strengths comes from the approach's hope for human beings. In this context, at the core of the empowerment approach are the foundations of Carl Rogers' person-centered theory based on a humanistic perspective. In person-centered theory, there is an emphasis on the innate goodness and responsibilities of each individual (Gray, 2011).

BASIC ASSUMPTIONS OF RETROFITTING

The empowerment approach is based on 4 basic assumptions:

Exposure to oppression is a structurally based phenomenon that affects individuals and communities. Oppression is an important phenomenon that affects individuals and communities. Oppression is a process that is characterized by psychological conditions such as depression, low self-perception and low self-efficacy in individuals and groups. Individuals and groups who are oppressed think that they do not have a choice and respond to oppressive groups to the extent of their own possibilities. The success of their resistance to oppression depends on their solidarity with other oppressed communities and the idea of unity (Lee and Hudson, 2011). The PCS model developed by Thompson (2020) is based on this assumption. According to Thompson (2020), P is the emotions, thoughts, behaviors, and actions at the personal level. In this approach, the emotional, intellectual, and behavioral

view of the society is formed as a result of the person's experiences with the society. The person understands the society by copying their individual experiences. C is the cultural level of mutual processes such as seeing, thinking, and doing. This level is about shared points, so it produces values and patterns of thought and behavior, a default consensus about what is moral and what is immoral, conformity to social norms, and humor serves as a vehicle for communicating and reinforcing this culture. Therefore, shared values are prioritized first and foremost, and include elements such as religion and nationality. The structural level refers to the network of social divisions and the power relations so closely associated with them; it also relates to the ways in which oppression and discrimination are "institutionalized" (firmly established through patterns of thought, language and behaviour) and thus woven into the fabric of society. It refers to the broader level of social forces, the sociopolitical dimension of intertwined patterns of power and influence (Thompson, 2020). PCS analysis shows the different levels at which discrimination operates and how these levels reinforce each other, so that the social worker has the chance to observe large pressure groups and their individual dynamics.

Individuals, communities have opportunities to solve problems that arise suddenly, they are resistant to institutionalized pressure groups. Communities can defend themselves against the political and individual power of pressure groups by recognizing and integrating the power of the individuals who make them up. Thus, existing problems can be overcome and individuals can turn crisis moments into opportunities in each process (Teater, 2015: 70).

Empowerment involves focusing on individuals and their environment. As individuals become empowered, they begin to integrate with personal and environmental resources. In Thompson (2020)'s PCS model, the transitive C dimension is important between individual values and political power groups, where there are spiritual values. Empowerment in the cultural dimension increases one's resistance to political groups. In empowerment, the oppressor should be empowered as well as the oppressed (Lee and Hudson, 2011). Although the oppressive groups do not apply to the counselor, they lose their ground as a result of the effectiveness of anti-oppression groups and individuals. Thus, the external effects of the oppressors decrease and they come under the influence of internal psychological processes. Ultimately, the individual who transforms his environment positively becomes empowered and the balance of power is formed.

Empowerment is both a process and a result. Caring, change, control, improvement have been the basic assumptions of social work, and empowerment uses these concepts. When

the counselor and the client talk together in a palliative manner and the client discovers who and what the problems stem from and the conditions that cause continuity, the client develops self-awareness. The client is now more empowered and when he/she is empowered, he/she starts to see the counselor as a teammate, not as someone in a higher authority than him/herself. On the other hand, it is a process to resist the obstacles and pressures in this process and to mobilize the people around him/her in this direction, and every process may not have a result, but the results initiate the empowerment of other individuals and groups (Howe, 2009:156).

REINFORCEMENT APPLICATION

The empowerment approach consists of implementation, assessment and intervention stages. Before the assessment process, the counselor and the client should establish a bond around common values. Anti-authoritarian feelings and limited motivation alone are not helpful factors in combating oppression. The counselor should be able to give convincing answers to questions such as 'Why am I here?', 'What can people like us do?' (Mullender, Ward and Fleming, 2013). For this reason, the empowerment process is a collaborative approach in which the client freely determines his/her own problems and the counselor conducts joint decision-making processes (Teater, 2015:71). According to Lee and Hudson (2011:163), it is the client's own will that initiates the intervention.

The counselor should not give power to the client. If the counselor gives power and takes it under his/her control, the power may suddenly disappear. In this case, the strengths and weaknesses of the client should be evaluated to ensure that the client is empowered in a process (Payne, 2020). In the evaluation phase, power has an effect on personal, interpersonal and sociopolitical levels. Therefore, there are different ways to understand power. The different dimension of power emerges in interpersonal relationships. For example, trying to realize your desire by force without the consent of another person. The counselor can understand from the narratives of the applicant that power is an element of oppression. In some cases, behind physical violence, threatening behaviors, there may be unwanted behaviors such as disrespectful behavior, indifference and manipulation. Therefore, the applicant's narrative and life story should be evaluated as a whole (Payne, 2020). Therefore, although the stories of the applicants do not include oppression, their past experiences and perceptions can lead them to the definition of oppression. Anti-oppression practice and advocacy are the cornerstones of the empowerment approach (Lee and Hudson, 2011).

Assessment is an action done together with the client in the process of increasing the level of critical consciousness about all dimensions of the problem. Reflective ideas are used in the intervention process to increase the level of consciousness (Duyan, 2016). In the first stage of the assessment, the counselor and the client engage in a dialectical interaction. The definition of the problem is represented by the different perspectives of the two parties. Joint decisions are taken by interviewing and road mapping. The counselor focuses on the individual ground of the client, and also looks at his/her relationship with his/her environment (political positions, social structure). The case is examined with an eclectic approach, especially the empowerment approach. The meaning that each approach adds to the individual and the intervention process should be evaluated in its conditions.

The first dimension of the assessment is that the social worker establishes a dynamic bond with the client due to the person's application or individual need. The physical, mental, social obstacles that restrict the client's environment are observed. It is determined whether the individual can overcome the problem on his own or with professional support. How he perceives his environment and the state of his power are important. In the second dimension, the individual, whose self-awareness develops with interventions, begins to enter into solidarity with individuals who are oppressed like him and who have to overcome obstacles. In some cases, they have even participated in joint action and non-governmental organizations (Duyan, 2016).

The intervention process varies depending on the nature and duration of the assessment process. The counselor and the client make some decisions and planning to combat personal, sociocultural barriers such as discrimination, oppression, stigmatization (Teater, 2015). The counselor is like a guide in this process, the interventions to be made are clear; however, more than one intervention varies depending on how much the client is strengthened by each obstacle. The plan can be changed to an alternative when there are unexpected situations. This is why flexibility is important in social work counseling.

LIMITATIONS OF THE EMPOWERMENT APPROACH

In the empowerment approach, the assessment and intervention processes start with the request of the applicant. Therefore, the individual who can take control of his/her own life, who realizes that something is going wrong in his/her life can be handled in this approach. In some cases, for example, in cases such as substance abuse or sexual abuse, other approaches are carried out with priority to repair the mental and physical damage that may

exist in the applicant rather than empowerment because the applicants are emotionally and socially abused. The empowerment approach can be used in the counseling process and evaluation stages of task-oriented, psychoanalytic, transactional approaches. In this process, it is important for the counselor to use power and reassuring language patterns in the therapeutic relationship with the client (Hasenfeld, 1987). For the client who can integrate with his environment by using his internal processes, the exploration of the environment begins. In this process, the social worker can do various activities other than counseling, including training. For clients who speak little or have difficulty in expressing themselves, visual descriptions and body language are part of the counseling.

Foucault (1974) brought a different perspective to the relationship between the client and the counselor. According to Foucault (1974), what is power for the counselor can be a stifling, one-sided communication for the client. Again, according to Foucault (1974), the meaning and effect of power can arise in situations of disagreement between the counselor and the client, in the search for justice. Therefore, the language of the therapeutic process should be determined according to the client. According to Foucault (1974), the concepts of power and empowerment should be freed from individual-oriented theories.

The counselor must consider the best interests of the client in the assessment process, but in some cases there may be a dilemma: is it possible to help the client in a situation where he/she is so restricted or overly abused that he/she may harm his/her environment?

When the counselor does not pay attention to the word patterns used in the therapeutic relationship, the client may misinterpret them (Greene et al., 2005). These are the five methods of strengthening language:

- o The language of cooperation versus the language of help
- o Language of ownership/property
- o Language of possibilities
- o Solution language
- o Language of elaboration and clarification

In the study of Ackerson and Harrison (2000), inequality, powerlessness and justice seeking are not seen as a limitation. In the research, social workers working in the field of mental health stated that the rules of the institution are not suitable for every client and that the support application is limited. The earthly and spiritual identity of the client is less emphasized. In some countries, institutional practices and various policies limit the empowerment approach and have led to poor results when working with communities.

CASE STUDY

Problem of the Study

Social workers encounter different psychosocial problem situations due to their profession. While dealing with the situations of their clients, they can reflect their individual wishes and emotional sides to the decision-making processes. The fact that the number of publications combining practice and theory in Turkey is low makes case studies important. As well as the material and moral deprivation of the clients, the mechanisms that push the professional staff to decision-making processes with the client are important. It is necessary to compare the practices with different theories.

Methodology of Study

A case report in social work involves documenting a specific client's situation, the interventions used, and the outcomes achieved. The methodology includes selecting a relevant and educational case, obtaining client consent, conducting a thorough assessment using social work theories, creating an intervention plan with clear goals, and evaluating the effectiveness of the intervention. Ethical considerations, such as confidentiality, informed consent, and cultural competence, are critical throughout the process. The case report concludes with reflections on lessons learned, recommendations for improving practice, and suggestions for further research. This methodology ensures that the case contributes to professional development and enhances social work practice. Since social work is a practice-based profession, sample cases and case studies will guide the professionals in the applications that can be made with individuals and groups.

The professional practices carried out in the social service centre were reported in a 6-month period and home, school visits were supported by visits to schools and hospitals. A descriptive case analysis in social work is a systematic method of examining a particular case or client scenario to understand its various dimensions, identify issues, and reflect on the applied intervention strategies (Süleymanoğlu Kürüm ,2021). In this study, the priority of the professional is to understand the case in a descriptive way in terms of events and persons.

The case is a real case registered at the X Social Service Center.

G.I.: Born on 10.08.2003 in Üsküdar, the individual was harmonious, outgoing, talkative, respectful and had a high level of awareness for his age. It was understood that the child was able to express himself, had good relations with friends and relatives, and endeared himself to his environment in a short time.

R.I: Born on 13.10.1966 in Hacıpehlivan, father R.I. has a mildly timid, low self-expression

skills, easy-going and calm personality traits. R.I. describes his wife S.I. as an angry, irritable and restless person who is ready to argue at any moment, and states that she uses many antidepressant medications due to her extreme irritability.

S.I.: Born on 18.04.1965, mother S.I. was found to have a mild mental retardation, an irritable nature, frequently engaged in verbal conflicts with her husband and child during the interview, showed irritability and had a changeable mood. It was determined that she was not sufficient to meet the needs of the household and that the father mostly did the cooking, dishwashing, laundry, etc.

Under evaluation,

Upon the application of the father R.I., a social investigation was conducted at home. Apart from financial deprivation, it was revealed that the mother could not do housework and had poor communication with her husband and child. Although the father applied due to financial problems, it was determined that there were psychological, physical and social problems that limited the role of the father in the family.

Although the mother S.I. initially said that the family problems were not caused by her, she started to receive support from the medical social service unit of the hospital regarding her physical disability, medications and treatment.

It was understood that the father, R.I., was passive, had difficulty in communicating, and constantly did the cooking and cleaning work himself since he had no say in the family.

During the intervention phase

Social assistance support was received from the district governor's office to provide the family with healthy housing and to cover student expenses.

The father R.I. was assigned a caregiver from the Ministry of Health so that he could take his heart medication on time. They were facilitated to make doctor's appointments easily. With the new support, they moved to a larger house without heating problems, where they could live in harmony with their social environment. Thus, it was aimed to increase the family's self-esteem.

For the health problems of the mother S.I., the medical social service unit of the district hospital was contacted and her treatment was provided efficiently. The social worker monitored her health condition. In addition to the mother's health problems, individual and family meetings were held once a week with the family counselor working at the district social service unit in order to improve communication within the family, thus increasing the self-efficacy of family members.

It was determined that the daughter of the family, G.I., had problems adapting to her environment as a result of the family's migration from Istanbul to Biga and the impoverishment of the family due to being exposed to domestic verbal violence. It was aimed for the student to develop new relationships by changing the houses they lived in and the school where the child was enrolled. Care was taken to ensure that the new school was close to her home in order to benefit her. Cooperation was made with the school counselor to support healthy communication with the family and school lessons.

As a result of the interventions, R.I. stated that he met with her landlord, health institutions and his child's teachers with more self-confidence and that the effects of her illness decreased to some extent. G.I. stated that she spent more time with her family and that their communication was better. G.I. is studying in the physical therapy and rehabilitation department of a university in Istanbul, influenced by these intervention processes. Mother S.I. stated that she is now proud of her daughter and that she goes to her daughter all the time.

CONCLUSION

In the research process, it was understood that the process of increasing the moral motivation of the client and the professional staff was important. Positive developments in the health of the father and the daughter becoming open to reading and social communication are the desired outcomes. The ultimate goal of empowerment is self-sufficiency, and in this case a physically and emotionally backward family was able to become more independent in their decisions.

The intensive and empathic use of the social worker and the acceptance of the client ensured that the process was easy. Another important situation is whether the family can sustain the difficult situation or not, and for this, it may be considered to make observations to the family in monthly periods.

Empowerment theory in social work shares commonalities with several other theoretical frameworks but is distinct in its emphasis on client autonomy, self-determination, and social justice. While systems theory focuses on the impact of larger environmental factors, Person-in-Environment theory emphasizes holistic interactions between individuals and their surroundings. Cognitive-behavioral theory addresses individual cognitive patterns and behaviors, whereas the strengths-based perspective and empowerment both focus on building client strengths, but empowerment extends this focus to systemic advocacy and social change. All these theories, though different in approach, are complementary and can

be used in tandem to help social workers better understand and intervene in the complex lives of their clients. Especially in motivational speeches, cognitive therapy approaches and strength based perspective in revealing power were supported.

Many of these theories help people to make decisions about their own internal and external relationships. In the intervention approach, the influence of different theories has been felt in counselling. Ultimately, the empowerment approach is the theory that emphasises the environment and has a concern for social justice, thus providing arguments for policy makers to protect the family and evaluate it as a whole.

The empowerment approach is an approach that allows the focus of the person to turn from himself to his environment. It is a process of discovering his surroundings, starting from himself. Other approaches can be used eclectically in counseling processes. Although the strengths of the individual can be determined and the individual can take control of his life, it is not possible for this to result positively in every therapeutic relationship. The social worker's personal values, assumptions may be incomplete or incorrect; he may not even know the method and approach he uses. Therefore, it is a necessity for the social worker to make the next intervention accessible, as in the case example, in order for both the evaluation and the intervention to be carried out in a healthy way. A professional with strong theoretical foundations sets out on a challenging path with his client with his practices. While walking on this path, support from policy makers and the opportunities of the institution enables the social worker to reach his goals effectively. Network systems that the social worker cannot integrate will not work for the benefit of the whole. Therefore, the empowerment approach is an opportunity for the social worker to reveal his potential.

There are social changes that may hinder the empowerment approach. An evaluation process without ignoring them may not be healthy. These are perception of justice and postmodernism. Broad social policies for them will complement social service practices.

The empowerment approach in social work is a valuable framework for addressing the challenges faced by individuals, families, and communities. By prioritizing self-determination, personal growth, and resilience, this approach enables clients to navigate immediate difficulties while building lasting capacities for self-reliance and advocacy. For individuals facing systemic or personal oppression, empowerment offers a transformative pathway that allows them to redefine their role and agency within their environments.

In the context of postmodernism, empowerment aligns with the recognition of diverse perspectives and the deconstruction of singular, authoritative narratives. Postmodernism

values multiple truths and acknowledges the complexity of individual identities and experiences. This pluralistic perspective enhances empowerment by allowing social workers to honor clients' unique stories, voices, and self-determined goals, rather than imposing a one-size-fits-all model. In a postmodern framework, empowerment is about giving clients the tools to construct their own narratives and make meaningful choices, fostering a sense of agency that respects their identities and social contexts. Social workers, therefore, act as facilitators rather than authoritative figures, empowering clients to find personal meaning and agency amid complex social realities.

Justice is another core tenet of the empowerment approach, deeply intertwined with the principles of equity and human rights. Social work inherently seeks to address inequalities, and the empowerment approach provides a method for clients to reclaim power and confront injustices that may restrict their lives. Empowerment within a justice-oriented framework promotes fairness by working to dismantle the barriers that perpetuate disadvantage. It emphasizes the social worker's role in advocating not only for individuals but also for systemic changes that can address the root causes of social inequalities, such as poverty, discrimination, and lack of access to resources.

Empowerment, viewed through a justice lens, is about enabling clients to become active agents in their fight for rights and dignity. In cases where individuals experience oppression, this approach provides tools for resistance and resilience, helping them navigate oppressive systems while advocating for broader social change. Social workers are instrumental in this process, supporting clients in developing self-advocacy skills and connecting them with resources that foster greater autonomy. Justice-based empowerment also extends to community empowerment, where collective action can challenge societal structures that perpetuate inequality.

Moreover, the empowerment approach's adaptability allows it to be integrated with various social work theories and practices, ensuring that interventions are uniquely tailored to each client. This flexibility enhances its effectiveness, especially in postmodern and justice-oriented contexts, by acknowledging the interplay of individual and structural factors. However, it is important to recognize that empowerment may not always yield immediate results. The journey towards empowerment is often gradual, requiring patience, sustained support, and continuous reflection on the social worker's part to ensure that personal biases and assumptions do not hinder the empowerment process.

Ultimately, the empowerment approach represents a commitment to human dignity,

equity, and the belief that every individual has the potential to overcome adversity. It aligns with the core values of social work by advocating for both personal and systemic transformation, promoting a society where individuals are empowered to contribute to their own well-being and the well-being of others. As social work continues to evolve, particularly within postmodern and justice frameworks, empowerment remains a vital strategy for advancing individual and collective resilience, equity, and social harmony.

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